

Irrational Beliefs and Depressive Symptoms in Adolescents: Examining the Mediating Role of Self Image

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ABSTRACT: The present study examined the role of self-image as a mediator in the relationships between irrational beliefs and depressive symptoms in adolescents. The sample was comprised of 1000 bilingual adolescent students (aged 13 to 19 years), males (45%) and females (55%). They were urban residents of Lahore between the age of 13 and 19 years, with average age of 16.09 years (S.D. = 1.75). The participants were taken from a total of fifteen diverse English medium schools, colleges, and tuition centers in Lahore, Pakistan. They completed a demographic information sheet, Irrational Belief Test (Jones, 1968), Beck Depression Inventory-II (Beck et al., 1996) and Offer's Self Image Questionnaire (Offer et al., 1989). Structural Equation Modeling indicated that self-image played a fully mediating role between demand for approval and depressive symptoms as well as anxious overconcern and depressive symptoms. Furthermore, self-image partially mediated between frustration reaction, problem avoidance, helplessness for change, perfectionism and depressive symptoms. The findings shed light on the importance of personality trait (self-image) in linking the cognitive beliefs and mental health. The study has implications for counselors, clinicians and school psychologists as it highlights the necessity of rational counselling.

Key words: Depressive symptoms, Depression, Irrational Beliefs, Mediation, Self-Image.

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1. Introduction

In the complex landscape of adolescent mental health, the interplay between irrational beliefs and depressive symptoms stands as a focal point of investigation, offering profound insights into understanding and addressing the challenges faced by this vulnerable demographic. This research delves into the intricate dynamics of this relationship within the context of study settings, shedding light on a pivotal mediator: self-image. Adolescence, characterized by rapid cognitive, emotional, and social development, serves as a critical period where beliefs about oneself and the world can significantly impact psychological well-being. By exploring the mediating role of self-image, this study not only unveils a crucial mechanism in the manifestation of depressive symptoms but also opens avenues for targeted interventions aimed at bolstering adolescent mental health. Through a synthesis of empirical evidence and theoretical frameworks, this research embarks on an investigation to unravel the nuanced connections between irrational beliefs, depressive symptoms, and self-image, offering a compelling narrative and its results promise to inspire readers within the realms of psychology and beyond.

Irrational Beliefs are considered to be pertinent particularly in the etiopathology of depression and they have also been linked to the self-image of an individual (Podina et al., 2015). This becomes even more crucial when one is undergoing transition during adolescence (Marcotte, 1996). The self-image of an individual is characterized as the summation of idiosyncratic self-insights regarding adjustment in various areas of life, social attitudes, and intellectual functioning (Offer et al., 1989). Fundamentally, it is the phenomenological development of distinct experiences of functioning in several social and psychological realms. During adolescence, self-image plays a predominantly vital role as it is during this developmental stage that reorganization of the self and relationships is extensively carried out (Schimmenti et al., 2014).

Studies have discovered the association of low self-image with several problematic behaviors and psychiatric indicators such as depressive symptoms (Korhonen et al., 2001; Erkolahiti et al., 2003), suicidal ideation (Eskin et al., 2007; Laukkanen et al., 2005), eating disorders (Erkolahiti et al., 2002; Steinhausen & Vollrath, 1993), social anxiety disorder (Di Blasi et al., 2015), and substance use disorders (Laukkanen et al., 2001; Naumovska & Bonevski, 2012) during adolescence.

In order to advance in the domain of psychological assessment of adolescents, Offer and colleagues (Offer et al., 1989) introduced Offer Self-Image Questionnaire (OSIQ), a multifaceted tool that tested the different facets of self-image. This tool has been used in a multitude of studies (Di Blasi et al., 2015) on adolescents, chiefly to discover mental health and self-development among adolescents.

Psychopathology is said to comprise of underlying mechanisms characterized by maladaptive beliefs and irrational cognitions. These beliefs serve as obstacles preventing people from achieving their goals and increasing their vulnerability to experience psychological disorders (Ellis, 1994). The ABC model proposes that core irrational beliefs (such as "The reason for someone rejecting or disliking me is that I am a useless or immoral individual"), are deemed to create particular interference in the processing of activating events (A) (for instance, the termination of a relationship), triggering definite

illogical beliefs (B) (“I am a useless individual”) which in turn bring adverse consequences (C) (such as distressful and depressed mood) (Ellis, 1994). Hence, illogical thinking results in distress.

Irrational beliefs were under special scrutiny as part of the etiology of depression. The four constituents of irrationality were deconstructed by Ellis (1994). These included demandingness, awfulizing, self-downing, and catastrophizing. Demandingness was characterized as the absolutistic necessity that an individual or circumstance has to remain in a specific manner. Self-downing was explained as universal negative self-criticism and evaluation. These two were identified as the fundamental vulnerability influences for depression. In general, researchers have discovered a positive association between depression and irrational beliefs (Nelson, 1977; Prud'homme & Barron, 1992). Depressed individuals were found to have a higher prevalence of illogical thinking as opposed to individuals who were not depressed (McDermut et al., 2006). Moreover, longitudinal studies have provided supplementary evidence that indicates how illogical beliefs interact with failure expectations (Marcotte, 1996; Browne et al., 2010) or stressful events (Shapero et al., 2014) and predict the signs of depression after a three month interval following the negative event. Irrational beliefs are said to be quite commonly experienced among the general population (Chan & Sun, 2021). However, a psychological disorder is not developed by all individuals with irrational beliefs. This may occur either because of the lack of interaction with stressors (Goh & Agius, 2010) and somewhat because of resilience factors that act as buffers protecting an individual from psychological disorders.

Topical researches indicate that self-compassion might act as a potential protective factor preventing the transition of irrational beliefs to depression. Self-compassion encompasses consideration and compassion that is self-directed (Neff, 2003). Numerous studies have proven the advantageous influence of self-compassion on an individual's subjective wellbeing, optimism, life satisfaction and positive affect (Neely et al., 2009; Neff et al., 2007). It has been negatively linked to depression and its vulnerability factors, such as rumination (Raes, 2010). The relevance of this concept is further backed-up by experimental manipulations studies, some results indicating that self-compassion instructions reduce depressive mood ratings, even more so than standard emotion regulation strategies such as reappraisal and acceptance (Diedrich et al., 2014).

Neff (2003) identified that self-compassion has three major constituents namely mindfulness, self-kindness, and common humanity. Mindfulness is reflected in a stable perspective of cognitions and feelings. Mindful people do not indulge in over-identification with their cognitions and feelings. Self-kindness encompasses warmth (that is self-directed) and introspection (self-awareness and comprehension) during adverse circumstances. Self-kindness is characterized by gentle self-treatment and a kind acceptance of reality. Common humanity entails recognizing one's negative experiences as part of a shared human experience which challenges most human beings. Recent studies on self-compassion have shown that its constituents are conceptually distinct, and most importantly relate differently to depression. One study found that self-kindness had a comparatively strong association with depression as opposed to the other constituents (Mills et al., 2007). Another study revealed that only two constituents (mindfulness and self-kindness) were

actually linked to depression (Van Dam et al., 2011). This implies that each constituent of self-compassion is likely to have a unique relationship with depression.

A limited quantity of studies exist about irrational beliefs and on what enhances the “cognitive immunity” of irrational individuals against psychological disorders particularly depression. Among the prominent protective factors are adaptive or rational beliefs that are dogmatic, shaped empirically, and flexible ways of thinking (for instance, “It is preferable for things to be easier, however, I am capable of tolerating it if that does not happen” instead of “It must be easy”). The major protective factors include a preferential way of thinking and unconditional self-acceptance. These prevent the transition of irrational beliefs to depression. Other acknowledged protective factors also include positive life events (Dixon & Reid, 2000). Moreover, an internal locus of control (Johnson & Sarason, 1978), social problem solving capabilities (Nezu & Ronan, 1988), and high self-esteem (Çivitci, 2010) are additional protective factors. Conversely, these variables have been associated with an extensive array of psychological disorders apart from depression, and a limited number of them have a cognitive nature. Thus, it may be concluded from reviewing literature that irrational beliefs increase vulnerability to depression. However, the literature does not shed much light on the aspects that may improve the “cognitive immunity” of irrational people against depression. Hence, the present study can help to bridge this gap in knowledge by examining the role of self-image as a mediator between irrational beliefs and depressing effect. The mediating effect of self-image and its efficacy in enhancing cognitive immunity needs to be examined.

Hypothesis

Self-image is likely to serve as a mediating variable between irrational beliefs and depressive symptoms.

2. Method

Participants

In the present study, the participants were 1000 adolescent students, males (45%) and females (55%), urban residents of Lahore between the age of 13 and 19 years, with average age of 16.09 years (S.D. = 1.75). Although, data from 1100 students were collected but only 1000 questionnaires were completed which were included in the research sample. The participants were taken from a total of fifteen diverse English medium schools, colleges, and tuition centers in Lahore. All the participants were a part of diverse socio-economic classes. Furthermore, demographic information was also gathered (see Table 1).

Table 1: Sample Characteristics

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Valid %</i>
Age	16.09	1.74		
Gender				
Male			447	44.7
Female			553	55.3
Academic Level	11.86	9.78		
Number of Sibling				
Birth Order				
First Born			400	40.7
Middle born			308	31.3
Last born			258	26.2
Father's education				
Father's occupation	8.5	15.76		
Mother's education	9.45	23.84		
Mother's occupation	13.03	21.11		
Family system				
Single			723	72.3
Joint			263	26.3

Measures

Irrational Belief Test (IBT). Irrational Belief Test was used to assess the irrational beliefs of male and female adolescents. The English Version of IBT was used in the research. Jones (1968) originally developed Irrational Belief Test (IBT). It consisted of 100 items, which were equally divided into ten groups and covered 10 different dimensions of irrationality. The ratings on the Irrational Belief Test (IBT) is taken on a 5 point Likert scale ranging from 1 (Disagree Strongly) to 5 (Agree Strongly). The 10 subscales are as follows:

1. Demand for Approval (DA) assesses an individual's need to gain love and approval from others in the society.
2. High Self Expectation (HSE) assess the criteria for being considered a worthy individual (adequacy, competency, and achievement in a multitude of aspects).
3. Blame Proneness (BP) measures the tendency to blame and punish evil individuals for their immoral actions.
4. Frustration Reaction (FR) measures the tendency to catastrophize circumstances when they are not going in a favorable direction.
5. Emotional Irresponsibility (EI) assesses the external causation of unhappiness and the people's lack of control over their emotional grievances.
6. Anxious Overconcern (AO) assesses the tendency to ruminate over fearful or dangerous stimulus and remain worried about the likelihood of its manifestation.
7. Problem Avoidance (PA) measures the propensity to indulge in the avoidance of responsibilities and obstacles instead of facing them.
8. Dependency (D) measures the extent of dependence and reliance on other people (who are perceived as stronger) to meet personal needs.
9. Helplessness for Change (HC) assesses the influence of an individual's past history and high impact events on the present behavior.

10. Perfectionism (P) measures the propensity to seek perfect solutions to problems and categorizing it as disastrous if this does not occur.

The test gives separate score for each subtest and a total score including all scales scores. Every subscale has a different cut off point, above which scores on the test show the presence and strength of irrational beliefs and increase in irrationality. Jones (1968) stated internal consistency approximates from .66 to .80, test-retest reliability (0.92) and a concurrent validity coefficient (0.61) obtained with ratings of psychiatric problems.

Offer's Self Image Questionnaire (OSIQ). It was applied to assess the self image of male and female adolescents between ages 13-19 years. In the West, this tool has been extensively applied in psychiatry for assessing self-esteem in adolescents. This tool is developed on the premise of adolescent developmental and growth perceived from the lens of the psychodynamic theory. It is based on the behavioral observation of healthy young individuals (Offer et al., 1989).

The 130 items of OSIQ covers 12 areas of adolescent's life based on theory, clinical experience and review of empirical findings. It includes 12 subscales they are: Impulse Control subscale (S1) assesses the degree of strength of an adolescent's ego to withstand the stressors present in internal as well as external surroundings. Emotional Tone (S2) subscale assesses the level of affection and the harmonious nature of one's psychic structure. It also assesses the degree of emotional fluctuation as compared to feelings which persist in a more stable state. Body image (S3) subscale indicates the degree of adolescents' adjustment to their bodies. Social Relationships (S4) subscale measures patterns among friendships and object relations. Morals subscale (S5) measures the extent to which the conscience or superego has developed. Sexual attitudes (S6) subscale evaluates the behavior, attitudes and feelings of adolescents towards the opposite gender. Family relations (S7) subscale evaluates the feelings of adolescents toward their parents and the type of relationship they share with them. It also evaluates the general home atmosphere with regard to emotional expression. Mastery of External World (S8) subscale assesses an adolescents' adaptation to their immediate surroundings. Vocational or Educational Goals (S9) subscale measures an adolescent's accomplishment in learning tasks and planning their future vocational goals. Emotional Health (S10) subscale identifies emotional health as the absence of severe psychopathology. Superior Adjustment (S11) subscale evaluates an adolescents' level of coping with self, other people and the world. This subscale also assesses ego strength. Idealism (S12) subscale measures an adolescent's willingness to help others.

It takes 40-45 minutes in the administration, and has been standardized on the Pakistani population for the age range of 13-19 years. Scoring is done on a 6 point Likert scale ranging between 1 (Describes me very well) to 6 (Does not describe me at all). The OSIQ gives only subscale score, which is obtained by adding the score of items of each subscale. Negative items are scored reverse by subtracting the subject's response from 7. Every subscale of this questionnaire has a cutoff standard score of 50. Scores less than 50 show that the adolescent have a high self image and a score greater than 50 shows that the adolescent have a low self image. Adding the obtained score of the subject on all the items

gives the scores of different subscales. Reliability coefficient of OSIQ ranges from 0.46 (Idealism scale) to 0.90 (Family Relationships) and validity ranges from .01 (Idealism scale) to 0.70 (Emotional Health scale). A high score on OSIQ represents low self image. Due to cultural problems, the subscale of Sexual Attitudes (S6) was excluded from the present study.

Beck Depression Inventory-II (BDI-II). It comprises twenty one items and it is characterized as a self-reporting assessment tool for gauging the severity of depression among adults as well as adolescents aged thirteen years and above (Beck et al, 1996). The items present in this scale evaluate lack of pleasure, sad mood, hopelessness, guilt, feeling like a failure, self-hatred/criticism, suicidal ideation, restlessness, lack of interest, poor decision making, worthlessness, fatigue, changes in appetite/sleeping pattern, irritability, difficulty in concentrating, and the lack of desire for sex . Approximately five to ten minutes are required for test administration. A four point scale (ranging from 0 to 3) is used for scoring. This scale has a total maximum score of sixty three. According to the level of depression, scores are divided in to four categories (minimal, mild, moderate, and severe depression).

The cut-off score of this scale is fourteen. A high score indicates that symptoms of depression (ranging from mild to severe) are present. When an examinee selects more than one option for an item, the option with the highest rating is considered. The test-retest reliability of this scale was found to be good (0.93). For out patients, the Cronbach alpha for reliability is 0.92 and for college students, it is 0.93. The construct validity between Beck Depression Inventory-II and Beck Hopelessness Scale is 0.68, validity among BDI-II and the Scale for Suicide Ideation is 0.37 and validity between BDI-II and Beck Anxiety scale is 0.60.

Procedure

Pilot study. A pilot study was conducted on 50 students (50% girls and 50% boys) age ranging from 13 to 16 years (mean age= 14years) from two English medium schools of Lahore. The purpose of the pilot study was to assess language conceptualization and comprehension of language as used in the tool, time required for administration, and the response of the authorities. The correlation research design was used in the study. The correlational approach is aimed at identifying the variables that occur together. Correlational research assesses the relationships among naturally occurring variables (Shaughnessy et al., 2012). Non probability purposive sampling method was applied in this research. Firstly, the concerned authorities were contacted for seeking permission to conduct the research. They were informed about the research, its significance, time involved, requirements and the procedure. Originally, there was a practical problem in getting the parental permission therefore, the administration of the institutions took the responsibility and gave their consent to take children of the respective schools as participants in the present research. Furthermore, verbal consent of the students was also taken to participate in the present research.

Group testing was used and the administration of the questionnaires was divided into two days because of the lengthy administration of the scales, which could not be

carried out in a single sitting. The subjects were administered Irrational Belief Test, Beck Depression Inventory-II and Demographic Form on first day. On second day, Offer's Self Image Questionnaire and Self Report Questionnaire were administered to the same subjects. In the Self Report Questionnaire 5 questions were asked from the students, which covered 5 different dimensions including that how they felt filling in the questionnaires, their language conceptualization and comprehension as used in the questionnaires, the time occupied by all questionnaires and their feedback for almost the whole process of administration. Most of the participants appreciated the concepts and found the questionnaires parsimonious and interesting. No major problems were reported. This pilot study also proved quite helpful in conducting the actual research study as the sexual attitude (S6) subscale of Offer's Self Image Questionnaire (OSIQ) was excluded from the original study because of the cultural differences.

Main Study. A total of 1100 participants were originally recruited from 15 different English medium educational institutions and various tuition centers of Lahore, but only 1000 subjects completed the questionnaires so only those who completed all questionnaires were included in the final study. Same procedure for permissions was carried out as for the pilot study. Furthermore, written consent was obtained from the educational institutions whereas only verbal consent was sorted from the tuition centers. The same administration procedure was followed. On average, the administration of the first day took one hour and the administration of the second day took one and a half hour in group testing situation.

Statistical Analyses. The relative efficacy of irrational beliefs and self-image in the prediction of depressive symptoms was estimated by means of Pearson Correlation between total score of IBT and BDI-II. ANOVA, Chi Square, Structural Equation Modeling and boot strapping technique were used. Mediation analyses were also carried out.

Table 2: Means, Standard Deviation and Intercorrelation among study variables (N =1000)

	Dem	Exp	Blam	Frust	Emot	Anx	Avo	Depen	Help	Perf	Image	Dep
Dem	1											
Exp	.30**	1										
Blam	.23**	.33**	1									
Frust	.19**	.33**	.18**	1								
Emot	.16**	.22**	.22**	.18**	1							
Anx	.06*	.14*	.11**	.13**	.06*	1						
Avo	.15*	.45**	.30**	.29**	.28**	.17**	1					
Depen	.13**	.07*	.23**	-.002	.06*	.01	.08*	1				
Help	.22**	.33**	.32**	.23**	.27**	.05	.36**	.07*	1			
Perf	.18**	.40**	.21**	.20	.29**	.09*	.36**	.08*	.37**	1		
Image	.13**	.19**	.09*	.23**	.05	.65**	.21**	-.01	.16**	.05	1	
Dep	.21**	.38**	.21**	.40**	.21**	.10**	.39**	.03	.29**	.26**	.30**	1
M	30.12	30.61	31.83	29.41	30.49	31.84	29.50	32.11	30.09	31.74	378.32	17.32
SD	4.22	5.41	5.14	5.16	4.28	10.59	5.28	11.08	5.49	5.63	80.94	8.91

Note: Dem=Demand, Expt= High self expectataion, Blam = Blame pronness, Frust= Frustration, Emot= Emotional instibility, Anx= Anxious overconcern, Avo =Problem avoidance, Depen=Dependency, Help = Helplessness, Perf= Perfectionism, Image = Self-image, Dep = Depression

3. Results

The data was evaluated for coding errors, missing values, and ascertaining normality assumptions in Table 2. Overall, internal consistencies (Cronbach's alpha) were low to moderate for all beliefs dimensions ($.60 < \alpha < .80$), self-image ($\alpha = .85$), and depression ($\alpha = .90$).

Univariate Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) did not indicate any group differences for demographic variables (e.g. age, gender & income) in terms of depression scores. Before creating an estimated model, a correlation analysis was performed between the variables. The objective was to eliminate any independent variables whose correlation was $> .7$ in absolute value, thus eliminating problems of multicollinearity and improving the ratio between the number of variables and the sample size.

In the present study, all irrational beliefs correlated moderately positively with self-image and depression (Table 2). Amid the personality factors, neuroticism correlated moderately with depression, while extraversion correlated negatively with anxiety. Furthermore, openness was negatively associated with anxiety, though conscientiousness was significantly negatively associated with depression and anxiety.

In order to evaluate the relative importance of the direct and indirect effects of irrational beliefs on self-image and depression, structural equation modeling was carried out through the Amos program. In order to test the model, the maximum likelihood estimation method was used. Byrne (2001) recommended several indices to test the model's fit. Regarding the goodness of fit index (GFI), the non-normed fit index (NNFI), the comparative fit index (CFI), some authors have recommended values higher than $.90$ (Kline, 2005), or higher than $.95$ (Hu & Bentler, 1999) for these indices as indicators of a good fit of the model. For root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA), values between $.05$ and $.08$ indicate an adequate fit of the model (Hair et al., 1995). Bootstrapping with the number of bootstrap samples set on 2000 was carried out to estimate 95% confidence intervals. A bootstrapping procedure using 2,000 re-samples was used to assess unconditional indirect effects. Bootstrapping is a nonparametric re-sampling procedure that is recommended for testing indirect effects (Preacher & Hayes, 2008). This is because it does not need the normality assumption of sampling distribution of the indirect effects to be fulfilled (Hayes, 2013). This procedure generates 95% bias-corrected and accelerated confidence intervals of the indirect effects. An indirect effect is considered significantly different from zero if zero is not contained within the lower and upper confidence intervals.

In the direct model, the paths from irrational beliefs to depression scores were estimated and we removed the non-significant paths. The model's goodness of fit was adequate according to the chi-squared test, as it was not significant, $\chi^2 (3.45) = .62, p > .05$. After this, we estimated the mediating role of self-image in the relation between irrational beliefs and depression and rerun the model. We removed those paths that were not significant until the indirect model presented a good fit according to the other indices used. The model's goodness of fit was adequate according to the chi-squared test, as it was not significant, $\chi^2 (11.08) = .13, p > .05$ (Table 3).

Table 3: Model Fitting

Final Model	Chi-square	df	CMIN/DF	<i>p</i>	GFI	CFI	NF1	RMSEA
Direct Model (M1)	3.50	5	.70	.62	.99	.99	.99	.000
Mediating (M2)	11.08	7	1.58	.13	.99	.99	.99	.02

The standardized estimates of all of the model's variables are shown in Figure 2. The results indicated that the relationship between demand for approval and depression was fully mediated by self-image because the direct effects decreased to non-significant level when the mediator (self-image) was inserted into the relationship (see table 4). Further, the relationship between anxious over concern and depression was also fully mediated by self-image because the direct effect reduced to non-significant level ($\beta = -.17$, n.s) when the mediator (self-image) was introduced into the relationship. The standardized indirect effects of demand for approval as well as anxious over concern on depression were .01 and .18 ($p < .001$; bias corrected 95% CI: .03–.35) respectively.

Table 4: Summary of the Hypotheses and Estimation of the Direct and Indirect effects

Hypotheses	Direct effects	Indirect effects	Results
Demand for approval >self-image>depression	.000(n.s)	.01*	Full mediation
Frustration reaction>self-image>depression	.21***	.03**	Partial mediation
Anxious over concern>self-image>depression	-.17(n.s)	.18***	Full mediation
Problem avoidance >self-image>depression	(.19)***	.02 *	Partial mediation
Helplessness for change>self-image>depression	.06*	.001 ***	Partial mediation
Perfectionism>self-image>depression	.06*	-.02***	Partial mediation

Note: * $P \leq .05$, ** $P \leq .01$, *** $P \leq .001$ or less

The standardized estimates related to the mediating role of self-image in the relationship between frustration intolerance and depression indicated a significant and direct relationship in the expected direction on self-image, and self-image behaviour also indicated a significant relationship in the anticipated direction on depression. It was found that self-image was partly playing a mediating role in the relationship between frustration intolerance and depression as the direct effects were still significant when the self-image was introduced in the model as a mediator. The standardized indirect effect of frustration on depression was significant.

The mediating role of self-image in the relationship between problem avoidance and depressions was calculated. The results indicated that self-image was playing a partially mediating role in the relationship between problem avoidance and depression. The results indicated a significant and direct relationship in the expected direction on self-image, and self-image behaviour also indicated a significant relationship in the expected direction on depression when self-image served as mediator in the model (Table 4). The standardized indirect effect of f problem avoidance on depression was significant.

The analysis regarding the mediating role of self-image in the relationship between helplessness for change and depression was conducted. The results indicated a significant and direct of helplessness for change on self-image and self-image also indicated a significant relationship in the expected direction on depression. The bootstrap statistic

indicated the standardized indirect effect of helplessness for change on depression was significant. Analysis showed that self-image was partially playing a mediating role in the relationship between helplessness for change and depression as the direct effects were significant when the mediator (self-image) was included into the model (Figure 2).

Finally, the mediating role of self-image was studied in the relationship between perfectionism and depression indicated a significant and direct relationship between perfectionism and self-image and self-image also indicated a statistically significant relationship in the expected direction on depression. The bootstrap statistic indicated the standardized indirect effect of perfectionism on depression was significant. This analysis showed that self-image was partially playing a mediating role in the relationship between perfectionism and depression as the direct effects were still significant when the mediator (organizational citizenship behaviour) was included into the model (Figure 2).

Figure 1: Hypothetical Figure/Model

Figure 2: Final model showing the mediating role of self image between irrational beliefs (demand for approval, and depression (Adolescents in Pakistan aged 13-19 years, N=1000, data collected in 2014)

Fig.2: Final Model Fit (CMIN/DF = 1.58; P = .13; GFI=.99; IFI = .99; CFI = .99; IFI = .998; RIMSEA = .02)

4. Discussion

Self-image played a fully mediating role between the demand for approval and depressive symptoms. Previous researches support this finding. Cramer (2009) found that positive self-image was linked to adaptive relationships. Furthermore, an increased demand for approval was found in those individuals with low self-image. Self-image was also found to play a fully mediating role between anxious over concern and depressive symptoms in the present study. In previous studies, low self-esteem in adolescents has been significantly correlated with symptoms of anxiety and depression. This implies that a high self-image may act as a protective factor against depression (Fiorilli et al., 2019; Nguyen et al., 2019). This finding has been confirmed and replicated by the present study.

Further analysis in the present study indicated that self-image partially mediated between frustration reaction, problem avoidance, helplessness for change, perfectionism and depressive symptoms. Saeed and Dawood (2013) found that low self-esteem was linked to frustration intolerance. Therefore, a high self-image is likely to act as a buffer against frustration reaction and mediate depressive symptoms. Nasiri et al., (2015) found low self-esteem to be linked with poor problem solving skills and problem avoidance. Likewise, in this study, self-image was discovered to partially mediate between problem avoidance and depressive symptoms. Experimental studies by Brockner et al., (1983) found that low self-esteem was linked to learnt helplessness to change and adapt according to demands of a given situation. Similarly, in this study, self-image was discovered to partially mediate between problem avoidance and depressive symptoms. Ghahramani et al., (2011) found that negative perfectionism was linked to low self-esteem and the being highly self-critical. In this study, self-image was revealed to partially mediate between perfectionism and depressive symptoms.

Limitations and Suggestions

- Social desirability bias is a risk factor of having participants respond to self-report questionnaires as they may try to portray themselves in a desirable way. To overcome this, researchers can plan observational or qualitative studies to determine if similar results are obtained.
- The application of results is limited to the adolescent student population in Lahore, Pakistan. The study can be conducted across different samples, regions, and cultures to enhance its generalizability.

Strengths of the Study

- A large sample size was taken helping to improve accuracy of the results.
- Sample was taken from multiple diverse educational institutes in Lahore helping to improve the representativeness of the sample.

Practical Implications

This study has far ranging implications for counselors, clinicians and school psychologists. This is because it has highlighted the necessity of counselling of rational ideas in the individual and group format to enhance students' emotional health and facilitate their growth in the educational and personal sphere.

5. Conclusion

Thus, the findings of the present study shed light on the importance of the personality trait (self-image) in linking the cognitive beliefs and mental health. The results showed that self-image played a fully mediating role between demand for approval and depressive symptoms as well as anxious over concern and depressive symptoms. Moreover, self-image was found to partially mediate between frustration reaction, problem avoidance, and helplessness for change, perfectionism and depressive symptoms.

Statement of Data Availability

Data supporting the findings of this research study are available within the present research article.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Informed Consent was taken from all the participants involved in this research study. Privacy and confidentiality of the collected data was ensured at all times and the rights of participants were protected. The authors have no conflict of interest to disclose.

Statement of Ethical Approval

This research was ethically approved to be carried out by the concerned research review board.

6. Statements and Declarations

Declaration of no conflict of interest:

On behalf of all authors, the corresponding author states that there is no conflict of interest. There have been no competing interests in the conduction and completion of this research study.

Disclosure Statement:

No funding has been received from any organization for the conduction and completion of this research study.

Authors' Notes:

We hereby declare that this manuscript has not been submitted anywhere else for publication.

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